

Research

Correlation of Antipsychotic Drugs with Periodontal Diseases in Schizophrenic Patient

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Abstract: The purpose of the present study was to find out if there is any correlation of antipsychotic drugs with periodontal disease in patients with Schizophrenia. The study population consisted of 24 patients who were newly diagnosed Schizophrenia and prescribed antipsychotic medications by a registered Psychiatrist. Participants were grouped as follows: Group A (n=12) includes Schizophrenic patients getting first generation antipsychotic medications and Group B (n=12) includes Schizophrenic patients getting second generation antipsychotic medications. The oral health status of the participants were determined by Plaque index and Community Periodontal Index (CPI). This study reveals that the mean plaque score was 0.74±0.1, 1.32±0.21, 1.87±0.4, 2.24±0.32, 2.64±0.17 in group A and 0.5±0.13, 0.73±0.18, 0.96±0.22, 1.29±0.24, 1.68±0.23 in group B, at 0,3,6,9,12 months respectively. Community Periodontal Index (CPI) shows that in group A, (50.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and calculus at 3 months, (91.7%) patients had gingival bleeding and (83.3%) calculus at 6 months, (100.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and calculus at 9 and 12 months respectively. In group B, (16.7%) patients had gingival bleeding and (8.32%) calculus at 3 months, (50.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and calculus at 6 months, (100.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and (66.7%) calculus at 9 months, (100.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and (75.0%) calculus at 12 months. In group A, periodontal pocket (42.0%) 1mm, (50.0%) 2mm, (58.0%) 3mm and (75.0%) 4mm at 0,3,6,9 and 12 months respectively. In group B, (100.0%) 1mm, (66.7%) 2mm, (50.0%) 3mm and (33.3%) 4mm at 0,3,6,9 and 12 months respectively. The clinical findings of this study demonstrate that there is difference in dental and periodontal conditions among the Schizophrenic patients getting first generation antipsychotics in Group A than those are getting second generation antipsychotics in Group B. More specifically, Group B Schizophrenic patients received second generation medications showed comparatively better dental and periodontal health conditions than Group A.

Keywords: Schizophrenic patient, Gingivitis, Periodontitis, Pocket depth

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Introduction

All periodontal tissues (gingiva, alveolar bone, periodontium, and tooth cementum) are affected by periodontal disease, which is a complicated illness [1]. If neglected, it may cause the alveolar bone surrounding the teeth to gradually erode, loosening and eventually resulting in the loss of teeth [2]. A number of systemic illnesses are to blame for a decline in dental health over the course of a lifetime. Psychiatric problems, for example, have a significant effect on oral health and can negatively impact an individual's eating, talking, and other social and psychological aspects of their life, as well as their quality of life, wellbeing, and self-esteem [3].

Numerous researches have been conducted to assess the state of dental health between mentally healthy individuals and psychiatric patients. Psychiatric patients have a higher incidence of oral problems, such as decreased periodontal attachment, heightened susceptibility to caries, tooth extractions, and fewer filled teeth [4-7]. This is due to a number of factors, including the kind and severity of psychiatric disorders, a lack of awareness of oral health issues, poor oral hygiene, a particular dental phobia, access issues to medical facilities, the negative effects of psychiatric medications, poor diet, self-neglect, and dental professionals' attitudes and knowledge regarding patients with psychiatric disorders. Additionally, these patients have trouble receiving dental care due to their lack of desire and indifference, poor compliance, inability to adjust to new prostheses, mobility issues, and dread of the procedure, inadequate communication, and financial concerns [8].

Psychiatric illnesses are accountable for lowering the state of overall health in addition to the oral health. It is estimated that over 450 million people globally suffer from a mental illness since mental health is essential to overall health. People from all walks of life and all countries are affected by mental illness. It has an impact on a person's whole behavior, changing perception and operating at an impaired level. Because to ignorance, stigma, fear, misconceptions, and unfavorable views, this group is frequently ignored [9].

The most common serious mental condition among the disorders of the mind is schizophrenia. Prior research has demonstrated that schizophrenia is a persistent mental illness marked by flare-ups and remissions that causes sufferers to become socially and professionally disabled. One of the top 10 causes of impairment in the population between the ages of 15 and 44, the disease affects 1% of the general population [4]. Schizophrenia has an annual incidence of 0.16 to 0.28 per 1,000 people. There are 4000 to 5000 cases per million, or 1.1% and 1.9% of cases for men and women, respectively. Urban and industrialized areas have higher rates of clinical symptom prevalence, morbidity, and severity than rural areas. Furthermore, while the incidence is the same across all socioeconomic classes, the prevalence is higher in lower socioeconomic levels. It is also the most complicated mental illness that humans have ever encountered. The majority of individuals with schizophrenia have a higher chance of dying as well as a number of medical co-morbidities, including obesity, lung cancer, heart disease, and emphysema [10-13].

There are numerous first- and second-generation antipsychotic medications available to treat schizophrenia. Many first-generation antipsychotics, including fluphenazine, haloperidol, thioridazine, sulpiride, and thiothixene, have been registered in Bangladesh. Because of their strong affinity for dopamine D2 receptors, all of the drugs in this generation cause extrapyramidal symptoms and have a considerable risk of tardive dyskinesia. While some are less successful in

treating negative symptoms of psychosis, they are effective in treating positive symptoms. Aripiprazole, clozapine, risperidone, olanzapine, quetiapine, ziprasidone, and amisulpride are the second-generation antipsychotics. Since these antipsychotics affect more than only the dopaminergic D2 receptor system, neurotransmitter activity is more balanced after administration. Regrettably, antipsychotics have a number of adverse effects in addition to their beneficial therapeutic effects [1].

Numerous researches have demonstrated the negative effects of psychiatric drugs. Psychotropic drugs may result in hypofunction of the salivary glands, which reduces salivation (dry mouth). Due to the unfavorable changes in the oral environment, this condition frequently causes the cariogenic microflora to intensify and speeds up the development of tooth decay [10]. In addition, they have been linked to the following conditions: bruxism, discolored tongue, parotiditis, fissured tongue, tongue atrophy, oral ulcers, stomatitis, gingivitis, glossitis, and dysgeusia [12]. Given that medication therapy for schizophrenia is a chronic illness that takes time to resolve, the likelihood of harm to one's dental health must be demonstrated. Therefore, the purpose of the present study will find out if there is any correlation of antipsychotic drugs with dental caries and periodontal disease in patients with Schizophrenia.

Materials and methods

Newly diagnosed schizophrenic patients from Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University's OPD and the National Institute of Mental Health in Dhaka, Bangladesh, were the subjects of this observational longitudinal comparison study. a licensed psychiatrist who diagnosed the patient as having schizophrenia and recommended first-generation antipsychotic drugs for group A and second-generation antipsychotic drugs for group B. technique of purposeful sampling. The following criteria are for inclusion: Schizophrenia patients who have been diagnosed by a licensed psychiatrist, those who have been prescribed medication by a psychiatrist but have not yet begun taking antipsychotics, patients who are willing to share information, patients who are male and female, and patients who are above the age of 18.

Study Procedure:

Diagnosed cases of Schizophrenia by a registered Psychiatrist were selected by above mentioned pre-determined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Schizophrenic patients who have been advised first generation antipsychotic medications in group A and advised second generation antipsychotic medications in group B were included.

For fulfillment the exclusion criteria, routine investigations (e.g. CBC, FBS, Chest x-ray, Dental OPG) and routine dental intra oral and extra oral clinical examinations was performed. After obtaining permission from the concerned authorities and consent from family members/ guardians of the patients, clinical examination was conducted in the department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics. Each individual made to sit on a dental chair and examined with the help of mouth mirror, explorer and CPI periodontal probe. Before clinical examination, demographic data and medical data was collected by interviewing the patient and family members. It includes age, sex, education level, occupation, socio economic status. In addition, they were questioned about their personal habits (e.g. smoking, tobacco, betel nut etc), oral hygiene habit (e.g. method, frequency and type of dentifrice) and any previous history of dental treatment according to questionnaire by investigator. Prior to the study pre-testing of questionnaire were carried out among the Schizophrenic patients to test the applicability of methodology.

Baseline data was recorded before the starting of antipsychotic medications. After recording baseline data, patients/ caregivers were instructed to start antipsychotic medications according to the prescription of Psychiatrist. At the same time, similar oral hygiene instructions were given to all patients or their caregivers by investigator for maintaining oral hygiene adequately. Subsequent data was collected at every 3 months, 6 months, 9 months and 12 months interval.

Results

Table I shows the distribution of the study patients by socio-demographic profile. It was observed that half (50.0%) patients belonged to age 25-30 years in both groups. The mean age was 32.9±7.4 years in group A and 32.7±7.4 years in group B. More than half (58.3%) patients were male in group A and 6(50.0%) in group B. One fourth (25.0%) patient's educational level was primary in both groups. Half (50.0%) patients come from rural area in both groups. One fourth (25.0%) patients economical status were lower middle class in group A and 5(41.67%) in group B. One third (33.33%) patients were home maker in group A and 5(41.67%) in group B. The difference was statistically not significant (p>0.05) between two groups.

Table II shows the distribution of the study patients by plaque score. In group A, plaque score were 12 (100.0%) good in at 0 days, 12(100.0%) fair in at 3 months and 12(100.0%) poor in at 12 moths respectively. In group B plaque score were 12(100.0%) good in at 0 days, 12(100.0%) fair in at 6 and 12 moths respectively.

Table III showed that the mean plaque score at 0 days was 0.74±0.1 in group A and 0.5±0.13 in group B. The mean plaque score at 3 months was 1.32±0.21 in group A and 0.73±0.18 in group B. The mean plaque score at 6 months was 1.87±0.4 in group A and 0.96±0.22 in group B. The mean plaque score at 9 months was 2.24±0.32 in group A and 1.29±0.24 in group B, respectively. The mean plaque score at 12 months was 2.64±0.17 in group A and 1.68±0.23 in group B. The difference was statistically significant (p<0.05) between two groups.

Table IV shows the distribution of the study patients by Community Periodontal Index (CPI). In group A 6(50.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and calculus in at 3 months. Majority (91.7%) patients had gingival bleeding and 10(83.3%) calculus in at 6 months. All (100.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and calculus in at 9 and 12 months respectively. In group B 2(16.7%) patients had gingival bleeding and 1(8.32) calculus in at 3 months. Half (50.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and calculus in at 6 months. All (100.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and 8(66.7%) calculus in at 9 months. All (100.0%) patients had gingival bleeding and 9(75.0%) calculus in at 12 months.

Table V shows the distribution of the study patients by periodontal pocket. In group A most of periodontal pocket were 5(42.0%) 1mm and 6(50.0%) 2mm in at 0 days, 7(58.0%) 3mm in at 6 months and 9(75.0%) 4mm in at 12 moths respectively. In group B most of periodontal pocket were 12(100.0%) 1mm in at 0 days, 8(66.7%) 2mm in at 3 months, 6(50.0%) 3mm in at 6 months and 4(33.3%) 4mm in at 12 moths respectively.

Table I: Distribution of the study patients by socio-demographic profile (n = 24)

	Group A (n=12)		Group B (n=12)		p value
	n	%	n	%	
Age (years)					
25-30	6	50.0	6	50.0	
31-35	3	25.0	3	25.0	
>35	3	25.0	3	25.0	
Mean ± SD	32.9±7.4		32.7±7.4		^a 0.948 ^{ns}
Range (min, max)	25, 48		24, 48		
Sex					
Male	7	58.3	6	50.0	^b 0.682 ^{ns}
Female	5	41.7	6	50.0	
Educational Level					
Illiterate	2	16.67	2	16.67	^b 1.000 ^{ns}
Primary	3	25.00	3	25.00	

Secondary	3	25.00	3	25.00	
Higher Secondary	2	16.67	2	16.67	
Graduate	2	16.67	2	16.67	
Social background					
Peri-Urban	4	33.33	4	33.33	
Urban	2	16.67	2	16.67	^b 1.000 ^{ns}
Rural	6	50.00	6	50.00	
Economical Status					
Lower Class	3	25.00	1	8.33	
Lower Middle Class	3	25.00	5	41.67	^b 0.606 ^{ns}
Middle Class	3	25.00	4	33.33	
Higher Middle Class	3	25.00	2	16.67	
Occupation					
Unemployed	4	33.33	3	25.00	
Home maker	4	33.33	5	41.67	^b 0.968 ^{ns}
Service holder	2	16.67	2	16.67	
Businessman	2	16.67	2	16.67	

Group A = First Generation Group B =Second Generation

ns= not significant

^ap value reached from Unpaired t-test

^bp value reached from Chi-square test

Table II: Distribution of the study patients by plaque score (n = 24)

Follow up	Group A (n=12)						Group B (n=12)					
	Good		Fair		Poor		Good		Fair		Poor	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
At 0 days	12	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	12	100	0	0.0	0	0.0
At 03 months	0	0.0	12	100.0	0	0.0	9	75.0	3	25.0	0	0.0
At 06 months	0	0.0	6	50.0	6	50.0	6	50.0	6	50.0	0	0.0
At 09 months	0	0.0	2	16.7	10	83.3	0	0.0	12	100.0	0	0.0
At 12 months	0	0.0	0	0.0	12	100.0	0	0.0	12	100.0	0	0.0

Table III: Distribution of the study patients by plaque score (n = 24)

Follow up	Group A (n=12)	Group B (n=12)	p value
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	
At 0 days	0.74±0.1	0.5±0.13	0.001 ^s
Range (min,max)	0.58,0.87	0.29,0.68	
At 03 months	1.32±0.21	0.73±0.18	0.001 ^s

Range (min,max)	0.92,1.67	0.42,1.04	
At 06 months	1.87±0.4	0.96±0.22	0.001 ^s
Range (min,max)	1.13,2.35	0.7,1.41	
At 09 months	2.24±0.32	1.29±0.24	0.001 ^s
Range (min,max)	1.42,2.67	0.96,1.79	
At 12 months	2.64±0.17	1.68±0.23	0.001 ^s
Range (min,max)	2.33,2.87	1.19,1.96	

s= significant

p value reached from Unpaired t-test

Table IV: Distribution of the study patients by Community Periodontal Index (CPI) (n=24)

Follow up	Group A (n=12)				Group B (n=12)			
	Gingival Bleeding		Calculus		Gingival Bleeding		Calculus	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
At 0 days	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
At 03 months	6	50.0	6	50.0	2	16.7	1	8.3
At 06 months	11	91.7	10	83.3	6	50.0	6	50.0
At 09 months	12	100.0	12	100.0	12	100.0	8	66.7
At 12 months	12	100.0	12	100.0	12	100.0	9	75.0

Table V: Distribution of the study patients by periodontal pocket (n=24)

Follow up	Group A (n=12)								Group B (n=12)							
	1mm		2mm		3mm		4mm		1mm		2mm		3mm		4mm	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
At 0 days	5	42.0	6	50.0	1	8.3	0	0.0	12	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
At 03 months	1	8.3	6	50.0	5	42.0	0	0.0	4	33.3	8	66.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
At 06 months	1	8.3	2	17.0	7	58.0	2	17.0	1	8.3	5	41.7	6	50.0	0	0.0
At 09 months	0	0.0	1	8.3	7	58.0	4	33.0	0	0.0	5	41.7	5	41.7	2	16.7
At 12 months	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	25.0	9	75.0	0	0.0	3	25.0	5	41.7	4	33.3

Discussion

The current study's findings supported the notion that individuals with schizophrenia who received first-generation antipsychotics had different periodontal diseases than those who received second-generation antipsychotics. Patients with schizophrenia who were on second-generation or unusual medicines had much better periodontal and dental

health. In this study, group B participants' plaque scores remained good to fair throughout the whole studied time (100%) but group A participants (those who got first-generation drugs) had a decline in their plaque scores from good to fair at three months to poor at twelve months. The reason could be that compared to second generation medications, the majority of first generation pharmaceuticals induce higher xerostomia. Antipsychotic drugs may result in both xerostomia and sialorrhea, according to a prior study [14]

The current investigation supports the hypothesis that when consumption times increase, the resultant hyposalivation exacerbates periodontal and dental disease. However, second-generation drugs like clozapine, a strong anticholinergic, are what cause hypersalivation throughout the day and at night [15]. The current study's findings further supported the high clinical scores—particularly for PI and BOP—that both groups possessed. Eltas A et al. [14], who discovered high PI, BOP, PPD, and DMFT scores in schizophrenia patients on antipsychotic drugs, further supports this condition. They found that xerostomia, which is more common in group A than group B, was the cause of these symptoms. Additionally, it was found that only 5.4% of Schizophrenic patients had a healthy periodontium, whereas 16.27% needed sophisticated periodontal therapy [16-17]. However, Mirza et al. [18] found that dental caries, gum inflammation, and dental caries affected 88%, 88%, and 65% of schizophrenia patients, respectively.

According to Velasco Ortega et al. [19] there is a connection between the negative psychopathological states of schizophrenia and a higher prevalence of tooth decay as a result of oral hygiene impairment. The majority of schizophrenia patients who take psychiatric drugs on a daily basis may have an impact on maintaining oral health, both conventional and atypical. Since the use of antiparkinsonic medications suppresses the effects of antipsychotic medications on parkinsonism, tremor, and akinesia, hyposalivation—an involuntary motor function—may hinder proper oral hygiene maintenance, which could result in the buildup of dental plaque. However, teeth and occlusion are also negatively impacted by tardive dyskinesia, a parafunctional activity of the oral, chewing, and tongue musculature brought on by both types of antipsychotic medications.

The current study also demonstrated that as time went on, Group A members' Community Periodontal Index (CPI) progressively declined. In Group A, nearly all of the patients experienced gingival bleeding and calculus at 9 and 12 months, respectively. However, after nine months, 66.7% of patients in Group B had calculus and 100% of patients experienced gingival hemorrhage. At 12 months, 75% of patients had calculus and 100% of patients experienced gingival bleeding. Thus, the Group A patients' high CPI index is consistent with earlier research [20-21]. The length of the disease process also led to an increase in the size of the periodontal pocket (75% in Group A and 33% in Group B at 12 months). Several reports have revealed that hyposalivation (xerostomia) increase the risk of periodontal disease [22,24].

According to the study's findings, people with schizophrenia who had hyposalivation, or decreased salivary flow rate, were more likely to develop periodontal disease than patients with normal salivary flow rates [14]. The new investigation corroborated the findings of earlier investigations. 90% of psychiatric inpatients (schizophrenia: 61%), according to a cross-sectional oral health survey conducted in central Taiwan using the community periodontal index (CPI), had poor periodontal health [25]. According to the World Health Organization's standardized dental evaluation, 98.5% of patients with chronic schizophrenia had poor periodontal health, according to another study conducted in Hong Kong [25]. However, because the majority of prior studies had small-to-medium sample sizes and the study participants were administered complex patterns of antipsychotics, there is currently little information available regarding the negative effects of antipsychotics and periodontal disease in patients with recently diagnosed schizophrenia [26-27]. Additionally, these patients have trouble receiving dental care due to their lack of desire, poor compliance, inability to adjust to new prostheses, mobility issues, dread of the procedure, inadequate communication, and financial concerns. The current study, like earlier research, revealed that individuals with schizophrenia have high DMFT scores and a high frequency of periodontal disease [14]. Furthermore, dental disorders frequently take a backseat in the overall medical care of individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia, despite the fact that they negatively affect a person's quality of life in general.

A multidisciplinary approach that addresses both oral and mental health is essential to the creation of dentistry programs. The goal of these programs is to raise awareness of oral health among psychiatric nurses and psychiatrists. For patients with schizophrenia, receiving professional dental care can usually improve dental issues.

Conclusion

The clinical results of this study show that the periodontal health of schizophrenic patients receiving first-generation antipsychotics (Group A) differs from that of patients receiving second-generation antipsychotics (Group B). More precisely, compared to Group A, the periodontal health conditions of Group B's schizophrenia patients using second-generation drugs were significantly better.

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